

1 **HIV-2 infection in dendritic cells.**

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8 We report here following microarray sequencing of total gene expression in a culture model of HIV-2
9 lentiviral infection induction of *CXCL10* in human dendritic cells resulting from infection with HIV-2.

10 Citations

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